

The Economic Buying Behaviour of Consumers at Shopping Malls - A Case Study of Mangaluru City

Mrs. Rovina Sharon Soans

Research Scholar, Department of MBA (TT), Mangalore University

Corresponding Author- Rovina Sharon Soans

Email: rovucm@gmail.com

Abstract:

Shopping Malls are played very important role in Indian Economy. They are the large spaces that combine consumer areas such as large national and local markets. Indian consumers are transforming to global consumer, who demand better facilities, international standard of services, top brand and quality. Thus shopping malls have bright future in India as well as in Mangalore City.

The review of data focuses on the emergence of Shopping Mall; influence on the consumer's economic buying behavior, and its influence on towards the economic development. The research design highlights deductive reasoning which is descriptive in nature and conducted with the help of primary and secondary data. The primary data has been collected with the help of questionnaire, from the consumer who visit the Shopping Mall. The secondary data for the study was collected from various journals. The respondents were selected using simple random sampling techniques. The data collected through questionnaire was analyzed by using percentage method. The study concludes that the consumers of the Mangalore are quite happy with overall Shopping mall experience. It is a sign of development of the Shopping mall and enhances the aspect of economic buying.

Keywords: Shopping Mall, Influencing Factors, Consumers, Buying, One Stop Shop.

Introduction:

In today's competitive environment consumer preferences and demand are changing rapidly. Shopping centers are large spaces that combine consumer areas such as large national or local markets, multi departmental stores, restaurant cafes. With this feature, the different needs of the consumers, by saving time on places which are easily. Mall provides a single platform for buying a range of necessary products, thereby reducing the cost in buying products, enhancing effectiveness in transaction, availing cost effective avenue for purchases. Today the word 'Mall' has become a part of people living in metro and big cities. Mall culture is mushrooming across the country's landscape at a faster pace. The craze of shopping malls ventured India in the late 90s and has seen tremendous growth over the years. Rising incomes, influence of consumerism and wide availability of product and services at single location malls had an impact on the buying behavior of the Indian consumers. Shopping mall are no longer associated with only shopping but have instead become places to meet friends, watch movies, eat, browse casually and so on. With the wide variety of activities available in a shopping mall it becomes important for retailers and mall administrators to understand purchasing patterns, time spent per visit, influencing factors towards shopping malls, awareness of the consumers etc, that helps to determine the shopping mall behavior among the consumer.

This particular study focuses on the economic buying behavior of consumers at shopping malls. The consumers buying behavior is affected by some factors such as income, taste, price, quality, quantity etc. But in the case of shopping malls there are various factors which

affected the consumers buying behavior which include brand name products, entertainment various facilities which is available in the shopping mall. The study also throws light on the consumers attitudes towards the shopping mall.

Review of Literature:

Uslu(2006) explains that most of the consumption is done in the shopping centers. It is the place where people can meet the needs as well as travel and enjoy. Shopping malls are shopping unit created by specially designed shops and stores with comfortable working environments and technical spaces for employees. It provides customers with the convenience of shopping, enjoying, having fun and resting, meeting the needs of consumers.

Ravindran Ram and Kumar (2009) investigated the decision-making styles of Indian shoppers in shopping malls. The survey was conducted to study the decision-making styles of Indian shoppers in shopping malls. The study also helps the managers of shopping malls to understand the underlying decision making styles of the shoppers in the malls and help them to craft their marketing strategies.

Mohammed soban(2011) shopping malls are improving their facilities day by day in order to attract customers. Shopping choices of customers vary according to their distinctive demographic attributes. In the United Kingdom, shopping malls are named "shopping plazas" or "shopping regions". Most of the shopping malls are situated in the main city areas, which are surrounded by open-air shopping streets in the United Kingdom.

Rukh-e-Zahra1 and Abdul Ghafoor Awan(2017) This research study was based on analyzing the relationship between consumer choices towards the choice of traditional market and shopping malls and it concluded that all the variables, consumer

purchase preference, consumer benefit perception, consumer lifestyle have strong relations to the shopping malls as compared to the traditional market and truly support the model of the study.

Ahmed and Mayya (2015) in Mangalore region on the perceptions of the customers of shopping malls clearly indicate that consumers have gained lot of benefits from organized retail on multiple counts like wider choice of products and well-known brands, one stop shopping, new market arrivals, festive offers, huge discounts, and other benefits.

Ramya and S A. Mohammed Ali (2016) found that consumer behaviour is influenced largely by economic factors such as personal income, family income, income expectations, savings, liquid asset of the consumer, consumer credit, and other economic factors such as business cycles, inflation, etc. also influence the consumer buying behaviour.

Elangovan and Sangeetha(2017)the main affecting factors towards mall have been identified as availability of parking facility, quality and variety of products, reasonable prices, mall ambiance, entertainments and discount offers. Availability of international brands and new products is also influenced consumers to visit shopping mall.

Bishnoi, Bharti and Gupta (2012) submitted a paper to investigate the consumer shopping behavior dimensions. It understands and deliberates consumer shopping behavior towards organized food and grocery stores, to have a better insight of consumers buying behavior. They suggested that marketers will have to understand the consumers 'shopping behavioral dimensions that will help them to tap the consumer in a better way.

Research Objectives

1. To describe the level of awareness of consumers towards shopping malls in Mangalore city.
2. To examine the factors which influence consumers shopping at malls in Mangalore city.
3. To interpret the consumers preferences towards the shopping malls in Mangalore city.

4. To analyze the consumers purchasing pattern at shopping malls in Mangalore city.
5. To ascertain the satisfaction level of consumers visiting at shopping malls in Mangalore city.

Research Methodology:

The study is descriptive in nature and conducted with the help of primary and secondary data. The primary data has been collected with the help of questionnaire which was the data from the consumer who visit the shopping mall. The respondents were selected using sample random sampling technique for the purpose of studying economic buying behavior of consumer at shopping malls in Mangalore city. The secondary data for the study was collected from various journals. The literature available in the field of shopping malls was studied. The data collected through the questionnaire was analyzed using percentage method.

Research Gap:

The study mainly focuses on to understand how changes occur in the mind set of consumers regarding shopping mall and their behaviour towards the shopping Mall. The boundary of this study is limited to Mangalore City. It is to assess the overall consumer satisfaction, response of consumer with regard to availability, quality of products and services offered at shopping mall and the comfort level of the respondents towards shopping Mall in Mangalore.

Statement of the Problem:

In this study of consumers economic buying behaviour has the greater importance for the retailers, which help them find the needs and wants of the consumer. Buying behaviour will vary from one consumer to another based on the offer that is provided. A study with shopping behaviour of consumers will help to understand the behaviour of mall visitors and also help the marketer to frame marketing strategies that can be additional capable of meeting their wants and needs.

Data Analysis & Interpretations

Sl. No.	Concept	Level of Measurement	Number of Respondents	percentage
Demographic Data : PART A				
1	Name			
2	Gender	Male	65	51%
		Female	40	49%
Total			105	100%
3	Marital Status	a) Single	60	59%
		b) Married	42	41%
		Widowed	0	0%
		Divorced	0	0%
Total			102	100%
4	Age	Less than 20	14	14%
		21 – 30	61	60%
		31- 40	19	18%
		Above 40	8	8%

Total			102	100
5	Education	Illiterate	3	3%
		Literate	4	4%
		PUC	9	8%
		Graduate	31	30%
		Post Graduate	52	50%
		Professional	1	1%
		Other	4	4%
Total			104	100
6	Occupation	Govt.Service	12	12%
		Business Class	17	16%
		Professional	40	39%
		Home Maker	15	14%
		Other	20	19%
Total			104	100%
7	Monthly Income	Less than 10,000	28	29%
		11,000- 20,000	30	31%
		21,000- 30,000	15	16%
		31,000- 40,000	8	8%
		Above 40,000	15	16%
Total			96	100%
8	Family Size	1 to 3	39	38%
		4 to 5	50	48%
		Above 6	15	14%
Total			104	100%
PART B Economic Buying Behaviour				
1	Awareness of the Shopping Mall	Yes	92	88%
		No	12	12%
Total			104	100%
2	Likeness towards shopping Mall	Yes	95	92%
		No	8	8%
Total			103	100%
3	Mode of Transport	Private Transport	64	62%
		Public Transport	40	38%
Total			104	100%
4	Type of Shopping Mall	City Center	28	27%
		Forum Mall	35	34%
		Bharat Mall	23	22%
		Other	17	17%
Total			103	100%
5	Day of Shopping	Yes	12	12%
		No	90	88%
Total			102	100%
6	Influence of Lowest Price	Yes	70	67%
		No	20	19%
		Undecided	14	14%
Total			104	100%
7	Local area shops v/s Shopping Mall	No	7	7%
		Yes	26	25%
		Availability of product you need.	17	17%
		Variety of product you need	23	23%
		Discount and Special Offers	26	25%
		Any other	3	3%
Total			103	100%
8	Price Variations	Yes	83	82%
		No	18	18%
Total			101	100%
9	Comparison of Prices	Often	18	18%
		Sometimes	63	62%

		Rare	21	20%
Total			102	100%
10	Brand name product	Yes	58	58%
		No	42	42%
Total			100	100%
11	Attraction towards Malls Save time by buying all items at one place	Strongly Agree	25	26%
		Agree	30	31%
		Neutral	10	10%
		Disagree	18	18%
		Strongly disagree	15	15%
Total			98	100%
	Accept all major credit cards	Strongly Agree	39	38%
		Agree	20	19%
		Neutral	15	15%
		Disagree	18	18%
		Strongly Disagree	10	18%
Total			102	100%
12	Sales Assistants	Attentive	31	30%
		Inattentive	10	10%
		Courteous	7	7%
		Rude	15	14%
		Co- operative	11	11%
		Indifferent	20	19%
		Efficient	5	5%
		Inefficient	4	4%
Total			103	100%
13	Information about consumer protection Law	Yes	98	94%
		No	6	6%
Total			104	100%

Table 01: Awareness of the Shopping Mall

Sl. No	Awareness of the shopping mall facility	Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Yes	92	88%
2	No	12	12%
Total		104	100

Source: Survey Data

The above table shows the Awareness of the shopping mall facility in the Mangalore city. The data interpreted that out of 104 respondents 92% of the respondents have the awareness of the shopping

mall facility in the Mangalore city and only few i.e.8% of respondents are not aware about the shopping mall facility in the Mangalore city.

Table: 02: Attractions towards Shopping Mall

Sl. No	Attraction towards mall	Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Save time by buying all items at one place		
	Strongly Agree	25	26
	Agree	30	31
	Neutral	10	10
	Disagree	18	18
	Strongly Disagree	15	15
Total		98	100
2	Accept all major credit cards		
	Strongly agree	39	38
	Agree	20	19
	Neutral	15	15
	Disagree	18	18
	Strongly Disagree	10	18
Total		102	100

Source: Survey Data

The consumers are attracted towards mall because of save the time by buying all items at one place and accept all major credit cards. 26% of the respondents are strongly agreed and 31% the respondents are agreed that shopping malls are saves

time by buying at one place. 38% respondents are strongly agreed and 19% of the respondents are agreed that the attraction towards mall increases because of it accepts all major credit cards.

Table 03: Preference of the Shopping Mall

Sl. No	Brand Name Product	Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Yes	58	58%
2	No	42	42%
Total		100	100

Source: Survey Data

Above table shows the consumers preference towards the brand name product from the shopping mall. 58% of the respondents are prefers only brand name product from the shopping malls. Out of 100

respondents 42 respondents i.e. 42% of the total respondents not prefers brand name product from the shopping malls.

Table 04: Influence of Lowest price in the Shopping Mall

Sl. No	Influence of lowest price	Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Yes	70	67%
2	No	20	19%
3	Undecided	14	14%
Total		104	100

Source: Survey data

The table shows that lowest price in the shopping mall attract the consumers. Most of the consumers suggested that lowest price attracts the consumers more than other shops.67% of the respondents suggested that lowest price offer in the shopping mall attracts the consumers more in buying from the shopping mall.

Findings of the study:

- The study shows that the people of the Mangalore city are ready to visit the shopping mall.
- They see shopping centers as a one stop destination for different purposes like eating, viewing cinema, hanging out, and for shopping.
- As I analyze it is clearly indicates that special offers, quality, variety and price are the major determinants which makes customers to visit shopping mall.
- There are also good numbers of customers who wish to buy branded products from the shopping mall.
- Most of the respondents prefer to go Forum mall (34%), followed by City Center (27%) and Bharat Mall (22%) in Mangalore city.
- It was found that the percentage of Male consumers (51%) was little higher than Female consumers (49%) which shows that men and women visit shopping malls in same ratio in Mangalore city.
- Majority of the respondents fall in the age group of 21 to 30 years (60%), followed by 31-40 age groups (18%) and less than 21 age groups (14%). The study also found that 8%

percentages of the respondents were into the age group above 40 years.

- The Study found that 50% of the respondents are Post Graduates, 31% were Graduates. The result further revealed that only 3% of the consumers are going to malls for buying Goods.
- Majority of the respondents visiting the mall were the Professionals (39%), and business class (17%)
- Majority of the Respondents having the nuclear family with 3 to 5 family members.
- Most of the respondents having the 11,000 to 20,000 Income level who prefers to malls.
- Most respondents expressed that the shopping malls are just not a place to shop due to its constant availability, but has also created an ideal environment for social interaction for people of all ages.
- Also shopping malls offer excellent parking facilities, create value for money, credit / debit card facilities, and so on. As a result, higher customer traffic is attracted towards shopping malls.
- The consumers are attracted towards the mall because it offers reasonable prices, saves time by buying from single roof and it accepts all major credit cards.
- Majority of the respondents have the awareness (88%) of the shopping mall facility in the Mangalore city.
- 67% of the respondents influenced by the lowest price offered by the shopping mall.

- The 62% of the consumers compare the prices offered by the shopping mall and local are shops.
- Majority of the Respondents are having the awareness of the consumer protection law (94%) in Mangalore city.

Suggestions:

1. Shopping malls are mainly for enjoyment, fun and shopping. So shopping malls should be made in such way that they should have more and more means of enjoyment and convenient to the consumers.
2. More variety of services should be provided in the mall, so that attract the consumers more.
3. Consumer services should be improved and promotional schemes should be provided from time to time for more sales in the shopping mall.
4. Shopping malls are mainly for enjoyment or fun. So shopping malls should be made in such a way that more and more means of enjoyment.
5. It should offer the reasonable prices to consumers.
6. Sales assistants should be render better services to the consumers.
7. As youngsters are the major consumers in shopping malls, shopping malls should try to focus on this category of consumers by offering different products and schemes for this class.
8. The mall parking should be improved so that parking can be done easily and it is safer for female shoppers.

Limitations:

1. It is cross-sectional study and not a longitudinal study.
2. Only a small sample size of the consumers were studied, which may not be enough to give correct picture.
3. The study is micro in nature, and its survey finding and observation cannot be generalized and may subject to change from time to time and place to place.
4. The scope of the study limited only to Mangalore city.
5. The study being based on data available from opinion of the respondents may suffer from the personal bias up to some extent.

Conclusion:

Every consumer has played a significant part in the development of shopping malls, where people used to purchase goods in one place. The retail centre has several stores with multiple brand options. Customers must be satisfied with the items' availability for them to buy them again. Shopping centres should focus on meeting customer expectations, which must be achieved by taking into account pricing, offers, coupons, etc. Consumers will all behave differently when it comes to making

purchases. Shopping malls in India have outstanding growth and have increasingly replaced the conventional department stores and retail outlets as a result of economic development and changes in consumer culture.

The main route for shoppers now is the malls. The key influencing variables for malls have been identified as parking facility accessibility, product quality and variety, affordable prices, mall ambience, entertainment options, and brand-name items for sale. Customers' decisions to visit shopping centres are also impacted by the availability of new products and international brands. As we know, customers' tastes and preferences are changing nowadays for a variety of reasons. In Mangalore City, mall construction is accelerating, and the rivalry grows up. According to this study, shoppers in Mangalore are generally satisfied with their mall experiences. They view it as a "One-Stop Shop" for a variety of brands and goods, making it quite comfortable. They receive a good value for their money spent in malls. Consumers used to contrast local markets with shopping malls in terms of amenities, deals, and prices. It is an indication of the growth of the shopping mall and the total shift in consumer desire.

References:

1. Ahmed and Sureshramana mayya (2015), "Buying Behaviour and the Perception of the customers of shopping mall-A case study of Mangalore Region" *International Journal of engineering and science*.5(9)pp-11-15:ISSN:2278-4721.
2. Elangovan.D and Sangeetha.R (2017), "A Study on consumers perception and preferences shopping malls in Coimbatore city." *International Journal of commerce and management Research* 3(2): pp-79-81:94-101:ISSN:348-0653.
3. Mohammed Ismail. El. Adky (2017), "Shopping malls attractiveness as egmentation approach" *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management* .35(11):pp-936-950:Doi:10.1108/095.
4. Mohammed Savanna Badar and Muhammed Organ (2018), "Shopping mall services and customers purchase in tension along with Demographics" *Journal of Market – Focused Management*, spring every HAL Id-D1839613.
5. Sebnem Burnaz,Y and Ilker Topcu(2011) "A Decision Support on Planning Retail Tenant Mix in Shopping Malls."
6. Uslu, Z (2006) ," Development of shopping centers: Konya example" *University of Selcuk, Institute of Science, Konya.*
7. Rush.e.zahra and Abdul Ghafur (2017),"Consumers behaviour towards the choice of shopping malls and traditional market" *Global Journal of Management, social*

- science and Humanities. 3(6) pp-373-394:ISSN:2520-7113.
8. Rukh-e-Zahra et.al(2017) “ Global Journal of Management, Social Sciences an Humanities” 373 Vol 3 (3):pp- 373-394: ISSN 2520-7113 (Print) ISSN 2520-712
 9. Rupesh kumar Tiwari et.al (2014), “Customer’s expectation towards shopping behaviou in retail outlets impact” International Journal of Research in Business Management (IMPACT: IJRBM) ISSN(E):2321-886X; ISSN(P): 2347-4572 :2(2) pp- 43-52
 10. Ankit Katrodia.M(2018),“Consumer Buying Behaviour at Shopping Malls: Does Gender matter?”Journal of Economics and Behavioural Studies.10 (1): pp-125-134: ISSN:2220:6 140.